

Modular programme for Education and Training
EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATOR

M#3 Inclusive Teaching

Andreas Bund (University of Luxembourg), Biljana Popeska (University of Luxembourg), Francis Ries (University of Sevilla) and the EduPASS Project Partners

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

TECHNICAL SHEET

Title: Modular programme for Education and Training: EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATOR. M#3 Inclusive Teaching

Authors: Andreas Bund (University of Luxembourg), Biljana Popeska (University of Luxembourg), Francis Ries (University of Sevilla) and the EduPASS Project Partners

Number of pages: 12

Year: 2024

Cite as: Bund, A., Popeska, B., Ries, F. & the EduPASS Project Partners (2024). Modular programme for Education and Training: EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATOR. M#3 Inclusive Teaching. EduPASS Project R#5 Project Output, 1-12.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14711972>

Project: Education for Physical Activity and Sport: Informal and Non-formal Settings

Project Coordinator: Claude Scheuer (until February 2023) and Andreas Bund (from February 2023)

Funder: European Commission

Programme: Erasmus+ Key Action 2: Cooperation for innovation and the exchange of good practices 2020

Action Type: Strategic Partnerships for Higher Education

Reference: 2021-2-LU01-KA220-HED-000051179

Timeline: 1 May 2022 – 31 October 2024

Project Sheet: <https://erasmus-plus.ec.europa.eu/es/projects/search/details/2021-2-LU01-KA220-HED-000051179>

For further information on the EduPASS Project please follow the link:

Website: <https://edupass-project.eu/>

PROJECT PARTNERS

The authors wish to acknowledge the contribution of the Education for Physical Activity and Sport: Informal and Non-formal Settings (EduPASS) project team for the development of the outputs here referenced for EduPASS (2024).

No.	Institution	Involved researchers
1	University of Luxembourg	Andreas Bund, Manolis Adamakis
2	Universidad de Sevilla	Francis Ries, Jerónimo García Fernández
3	Sport Ireland Coaching	Declan O’Leary
4	Willibald Gebhardt Institute	Roland Naul, Sebastian Brueckner
5	CEREPS	Katharina Groene
6	Valgo	Manuel Valcarce, Sergio García

Disclaimer: The European Commission's support to produce this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use, which may be made of the information contained therein.

Six Core Modules of EduPASS for Early Childhood Educators

The following are the proposed six core modules for Early Childhood Educators education and training programmes that were developed as part of the EduPASS Erasmus+ Project. The core modules should be seen as a flexible reference point which require contextual adaptation. Those individuals and/or organisations using the six core modules to develop learning opportunities for Early Childhood Educators should use the knowledge of their specific context to customise the modules to fit their needs, resources and objectives.

Each of the six EduPASS core modules proposed for ECE education and training programmes was developed building on the knowledge and insights, which can be found in the [European Quality Framework for Early Childhood Education and Care \(ECEC\)](#). The ECEC describes the most important the proposal for key principles of a [Quality Framework for Early Childhood Education and Care \(2014\)](#).

The respective module number and order in which the modules are presented in the table below do not indicate that modules must be introduced in this specific order, when implementing an Early Childhood Educator education and training programme. Rather the numbers simply serve as distinct denominators to help identify specific modules in the overall context of the EduPASS ECE education and training programme.

Core Module Overview

No	Module Title	Description
1	Daily Physical Activity and Play	<p>The module teaches the theoretical basis of the concept of holistic development of children, focusing on changes experienced by children aged 3 to 6 years.</p> <p>It emphasizes the importance of physical activity and play in children's overall development and well-being and highlights the benefits of physical activity during childhood, as well as the potential risks of inactivity on overall health. Additionally, recommendations for children's physical activity levels, strategies for implementation, and the development of skills for assessing the recommended daily physical activity level for children are provided.</p> <p>Finally, a theoretical background for developing intervention programs aimed at improving children's daily physical activity levels is presented. It includes practical workshops and the development of skills for designing and implementing programs to enhance children's daily physical activity levels.</p>

2	Principles of Educating Children	<p>This module aims to guarantee the comprehensive development of children through physical education. For this, different learning units, based mainly on the game, will be carried out such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • motor stories • music, dance and movement • energetic games • games with balls • activities that involve balance, development of laterality, coordination and body awareness • manipulative and construction games
3	Inclusive Teaching	<p>The module aims to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • introduce the theoretical foundations of the concept of inclusion. This includes the legal background (e.g., UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities and national legislation), the requirements and goals of inclusion, and didactic models, principles, methods, and strategies for inclusive teaching. • provide opportunities to practically apply and reflect about the principles, methods, and resources of inclusive teaching using specific teaching/case scenarios.
4	Fundamental Movement Skills, Play and Motor Skill Assessment	<p>The module aims to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • introduce the theoretical basics of the concept of fundamental movement skills and play and their importance for children. This includes the structure of fundamental movement skills, their role in children’s development, and didactic principles and methods to promote fundamental movement skills and play. • provide guidance on the practical use of the principles, methods, and resources of teaching/promoting fundamental movement skills and play. • introduce both the theoretical knowledge and the practical skills to objectively measure fundamental movement skills of children using motor tests
5	Hands-on Teaching	<p>This module is designed to enhance the practical skills of Early Childhood Educators through direct participation in learning activities. Through a hands-on approach, participants will develop key skills to foster high-quality interactions with children and create an inclusive learning environment.</p> <p>During the module, Early Childhood Educators will engage in interactive exercises and receive immediate feedback, allowing them to directly apply the pedagogical techniques learned to their educational settings. Strategies for observation and documentation, group dynamics management, and conflict resolution will be addressed, all focused on adapting pedagogical practices to the individual and collective needs of children.</p>

6	Plan, Reflect and Learn	<p>The application of teaching skills, observation and effective decision making is essential to fulfil teaching PAMPS for early childhood and is a cross-cutting capability that should be developed in all ECEs at each stage of their development. The ECE plans, evaluates and reflects each practice and event seeking improvements. In addition, this personal evaluation and reflection underpin a process of ongoing learning and professional development. An important element of this process is the ECE's efforts to with other ECEs in the process.</p> <p>Reflection plays a vital role in early childhood settings. It provides continuous professional development, support, and feedback for all members involved and gives ECEs a safe space to discuss challenging experiences and related feelings. It lays the groundwork for ongoing professional development through consistent self-reflection, community support, and emotional awareness. It's critical that educators can manage the feelings that come with stress to support children's development, communicate effectively with co-workers and families, and find job satisfaction.</p> <p>Questioning what learning and development is taking place to make meaning of what has been observed is crucial for ECE. ECE students should be able to describe why the events are significant to the child and to describe why this experience was important for the child involved.</p>
----------	--------------------------------	---

Core Module Structure

Core Module	Inclusive Teaching
Module Number	3
Core Module Aim	<p>The aim of the core module is to</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> to clarify the value of diversity and the importance of inclusion in early childhood education and to establish it as a general principle. to convey the knowledge, methods, and strategies for inclusive teaching in early childhood education using practical teaching/case scenarios.
Module Description	<p>The module consists of three courses:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Course 3.1: This course teaches the theoretical foundations of the concept of inclusion. This includes the legal background (e.g., UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities and national legislation), the requirements and goals of inclusion, and didactic models, principles, methods, and strategies for inclusive teaching. Course 3.2: In this course, the principles, methods, and resources of inclusive teaching are practically applied and reflected using specific teaching/case scenarios. Course 3.3: In this course, the practical experiences with inclusive teaching are reflected on and deepened in guided and independent formats of work.
Module Duration	30 hours
Facilities and Equipment	<p>Facilities: Seminar room and gym (accessible to all).</p> <p>Equipment: Equipment that can be modified or adapted to the individual needs and abilities of children or that is available in different variants</p>
Methodology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Class-based lectures and presentations, work in pairs and small groups, independent/self-directed working. Field-based sessions, peer teaching, specific teaching/case scenarios, work in small groups, independent/self-directed working.
Coaching Materials	Logbook / reflection book
Suggested Readings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Liebermann, L.J., Houston-Wilson, C., & Grenier, M. (2024). <i>Strategies for inclusion: Physical Education for everyone</i> (4th Ed.). Champaign, IL: Human Kinetics. Finkelstein, S., Sharma, U., & Furlonger, B. (2021). The inclusive practices of classroom teachers: A scoping review and thematic analysis. <i>International Journal of Inclusion</i>, 25(6), 735-762. Website: www.dippe.lu (Disentangling inclusion in Physical Education).
Evaluation	EduPASS Evaluation Tool for Early Childhood Educator Programmes
Module structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Course 3.1: Theoretical Foundations of Inclusive Teaching <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4 h Lecture Teaching Units

<p><i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 courses)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 4h Seminar Teaching Units ○ 2 h Self-Directed Working hours ● Course 3.2: Inclusive Teaching in Practice <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 10 h Workshop/Practical Teaching Units ● Course 3.3: Reflection and Deepening of Inclusive Teaching <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 4 h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 4 h Workshop/Practical Teaching Units ○ 2 h Self-Directed Working hours 					
<p>Learning outcomes <i>for Early Childhood Educators</i></p>	<p>The module will enable the Early Childhood Educator in training to build the following competencies (knowledge, skills, attitudes, values) which serve as a foundation when engaging with the children they teach:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="391 667 1404 1332"> <tr> <td data-bbox="391 667 890 909"> <p>Knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Children’s needs ● Children’s interests and preferences ● Pedagogical knowledge ● Motor development in childhood </td> <td data-bbox="890 667 1404 909"> <p>Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Providing a positive learning environment ● Communication skills ● Organizational skills ● Teaching / pedagogical skills </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="391 909 890 1332"> <p>Attitudes: <i>ECEs in training will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when engaging with children they teach:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Respecting children’s needs and interests ● Empathy ● Motivation ● Enthusiasm </td> <td data-bbox="890 909 1404 1332"> <p>Values: <i>ECEs in training will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging with children they teach:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Inclusion ● Valuing diversity </td> </tr> </table>		<p>Knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Children’s needs ● Children’s interests and preferences ● Pedagogical knowledge ● Motor development in childhood 	<p>Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Providing a positive learning environment ● Communication skills ● Organizational skills ● Teaching / pedagogical skills 	<p>Attitudes: <i>ECEs in training will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when engaging with children they teach:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Respecting children’s needs and interests ● Empathy ● Motivation ● Enthusiasm 	<p>Values: <i>ECEs in training will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging with children they teach:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Inclusion ● Valuing diversity
<p>Knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Children’s needs ● Children’s interests and preferences ● Pedagogical knowledge ● Motor development in childhood 	<p>Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Providing a positive learning environment ● Communication skills ● Organizational skills ● Teaching / pedagogical skills 					
<p>Attitudes: <i>ECEs in training will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when engaging with children they teach:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Respecting children’s needs and interests ● Empathy ● Motivation ● Enthusiasm 	<p>Values: <i>ECEs in training will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging with children they teach:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Inclusion ● Valuing diversity 					
<p>Learning outcomes <i>for children/learners</i></p>	<p>The module will enable the Early Childhood Educator in training to support the children they teach to develop the following competencies (knowledge, skills, attitudes, values):</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="391 1451 1404 2069"> <tr> <td data-bbox="391 1451 890 1664"> <p>Knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Social interaction ● Awareness about other children’s needs and preferences ● Diversity </td> <td data-bbox="890 1451 1404 1664"> <p>Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Fun and enjoyment ● Communication skills ● Cooperation skills </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="391 1664 890 2069"> <p>Attitudes: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Respecting other children’s needs and interests ● Empathy ● Enthusiasm Solidarity </td> <td data-bbox="890 1664 1404 2069"> <p>Values: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Inclusion ● Respect ● Cooperation </td> </tr> </table>		<p>Knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Social interaction ● Awareness about other children’s needs and preferences ● Diversity 	<p>Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Fun and enjoyment ● Communication skills ● Cooperation skills 	<p>Attitudes: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Respecting other children’s needs and interests ● Empathy ● Enthusiasm Solidarity 	<p>Values: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Inclusion ● Respect ● Cooperation
<p>Knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Social interaction ● Awareness about other children’s needs and preferences ● Diversity 	<p>Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Fun and enjoyment ● Communication skills ● Cooperation skills 					
<p>Attitudes: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Respecting other children’s needs and interests ● Empathy ● Enthusiasm Solidarity 	<p>Values: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Inclusion ● Respect ● Cooperation 					

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fair play • Honesty 	
<p>Module Outcomes <i>action oriented outcomes and results for educators (based on Quality Statements from EU Framework for Early Childhood Education and Care, 2014)</i></p>	<p>After successful completion of the module, the Early Childhood Educator in training will be able:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • to provide educational experiences that encourage participation of ALL children, ensures inclusion, and embrace diversity. • to provide educational experiences that ALL children enable to reach their full potential in a holistic way. • to collaborate with ALL children, colleagues and parents and reflect on his/her inclusive teaching practice. • to continuously monitor, evaluate and adapt his/her inclusive teaching practice, focused on what is in the best interest of ALL children. 	
<p>Connection to other Core Module</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Module 6: Plan, Reflect and Learn 	

Course Structure

Course Title	Theoretical Foundations of Inclusive Teaching		
Course Number	3.1		
Course Description / Main Objective	The course teaches the theoretical foundations of the concept of inclusion. This includes the legal background (e.g., UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities and national legislation), its development, the goals of inclusion, and particularly didactic models, principles, methods, and strategies for inclusive teaching. The main objective of this course is to emphasize the value and importance of inclusive teaching in early childhood education		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	L	4 h	Teaching Unit 1: Foundations of the Concept of Inclusion
	S	4 h	Teaching Unit 2: Discussion of the Concept of Inclusion
	SDL	2 h	Teaching Unit 3: Preparing an Inclusive Teaching Activity
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The concept of inclusion • Didactic models, principles, methods, and strategies of inclusive teaching 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interactive discussion of the concept of inclusion • From theory to practice – inclusion in “real world” settings • Advantages and disadvantages • possible barriers in practice, “trouble shooting” 	
	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preparing an inclusive teaching activity in pairs or small groups 	

Course Title	Inclusive Teaching in Practice		
Course Number	3.2		
Course Description / Main Objective	In this course, the principles, methods, and resources of inclusive teaching learned in course 3.1 are practically applied and reflected using specific teaching/case scenarios. The objective of the course is to understand how to plan and implement an inclusive teaching activity for children with special needs and/or disabilities.		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	W / PE	10 h	Teaching Unit 1: Implementing the Inclusive Teaching Activities
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Practical implementation of the inclusive teaching activities (pairs or small groups) 	

Course Title	Reflection and Deepening of Inclusive Teaching		
Course Number	3.3		
Course Description / Main Objective	In this course, the practical experiences with inclusive teaching gained in course 3.2 are discussed and reflected on in various work formats. The aim of this course is to give participants a deeper understanding of inclusion and to enable them to teach inclusively in various settings.		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	L	4 h	Teaching Unit 1: Guided Discussion and Reflection on Inclusive Teaching
	W	4 h	Teaching Unit 2: Group Discussion of the Concept on Inclusive Teaching
	SDL	2 h	Teaching Unit 3: Summary and Conclusion
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Guided discussion and reflection on inclusive teaching in different settings problem-solving strategies (“trouble shooting”). 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Group discussion on inclusion and inclusive teaching How to teach inclusively in “my” setting/field? 	
	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Independent summary and conclusions from the discussions (pairs or small groups) 	